

pH NEUTRALIZATION PROCESS MODELLING AND CONTROL USING LONG SHORT-TERM MEMORY NETWORK-BASED NONLINEAR MODEL PREDICTIVE CONTROL

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DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.14020911

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ABSTRACT

pH modelling and control are of great importance in many chemical and biological processes. However, achieving accurate pH control can be challenging using linear control methodologies due to the highly nonlinear nature of pH dynamics. This paper presents an innovative approach using Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) neural networks for modelling and control of the pH neutralization process. In this approach, an LSTM model was trained using input-output data collected from the pH process. The trained model was then employed as a prediction model in a nonlinear model predictive control (NMPC) algorithm. Finally, the designed LSTM-based NMPC was implemented on a simulation model of the pH process. Validation results demonstrated that the trained LSTM model achieved an excellent fit. The closed-loop results showed that LSTM-based NMPC exhibited superior setpoint tracking and disturbance rejection, comparable to the NMPC based on first principle (FP) model. However, the LSTM-based NMPC significantly outperformed the linear model predictive control (LMPC).

Keywords: pH neutralization process, LSTM, Nonlinear model predictive control, Recurrent neural network

INTRODUCTION

The pH neutralization process is widely used in the chemical, pharmaceutical, biological and waste management industries (Bamimore *et al.*, 2018). However, the pH process is inherently nonlinear with complex dynamics. This nonlinearity poses significant challenges for traditional control methods, often leading to suboptimal performance, instability, and difficulty in achieving perfect control. Conventional linear models and control strategies struggle to accurately capture the dynamic behavior of the pH process, resulting in poor regulatory performance, especially in the presence of disturbances and varying operating conditions.

To address these challenges, researchers are now exploring the use of Machine-learning model-based advanced control strategies that can handle the nonlinearity and the dynamic complexity of most chemical processes (Venkatasubramanian, 2019). Hermansson and Syafii (2015) gave a comprehensive review of the applications of different Neural network modeling based predictive control to pH neutralization processes. Ren *et al.* (2022) in their recent review gave an overview of the recent developments in neural network modeling and its use for NMPC design. Bamimore *et al.* (2021a) and Palancar *et al.* (1998) applied feedforward neural network for pH process control with satisfactory results. Sena *et al.* (2021) integrated Feedforward neural network with extended Kalman filter to achieve offset free control for a pH neutralization process. Bamimore *et al.* (2021b) presented a

comparative analysis of feedforward neural network (FFNN) and recurrent neural network (RNN) as applied to the experimental cascaded three tank system. Wu *et al.* (2022) developed a Lyapunov based NMPC that employs ensemble RNN as a prediction model with interesting results. A major limitation that has been identified with the studies that employed RNN is the exploding and vanishing gradient associated with RNN models.

Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) networks, a type of recurrent neural network (RNN), have been proposed to solve this problem because of its ability to model complex, nonlinear dynamic systems. However, the integration of LSTM networks into a Model Predictive Control (MPC) framework for real-time control remains an open research problem. Zarzycki and Ławryńczuk (2022) worked on a comparative study of LSTM and gated recurrent unit (GRU) as prediction models in NMPC. Alnaji *et al.* (2023) applied LSTM in designing NMPC for nonlinear time-delay systems with some useful results.

The research gap identified is that most previous studies utilized models from first principle and traditional control methods for pH process control. This study fills this gap by proposing a data-driven approach. Thus, the focus of this study is to develop and evaluate an LSTM-based Nonlinear Model Predictive Control (NMPC) strategy for the pH neutralization process, with the goal of achieving improved control performance, robustness, and adaptability compared to conventional control methods.

The rest of the paper is structured as follows: In Section 2, the theoretical framework of LSTM based NMPC is developed. The research methodology is presented in Section 3. The results and discussion are provided in Section 4, while some conclusions are drawn in Section 5.

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

Problem Statement

This study considers a pH system characterized by high nonlinearity and complex dynamics. Considering the complexity and the mathematical rigor involved in modeling the system from first principle, it is often necessary to develop a black box model of the system using

the pH is maintained at its setpoint in the face of unmeasured disturbances and process model mismatch while satisfying the system constraints.

Dynamic System Modelling using LSTM Neural Network Model

For the purpose of predictive controller design, the real plant is often modeled using the nonlinear autoregressive model, denoted as:

$$y_m(k) = f_m(y(k), \dots, y(k - \hat{n}_y), u(k), u(k - \hat{n}_u)) \quad (2)$$

where $f_m(\cdot)$ denotes the identified plant model, $y_m(k) \in \mathbb{R}^{m_y}$ is the model output, while \hat{n}_y and \hat{n}_u represent the

Figure 1: LSTM Neural Network Model Architecture

a data-driven approach. Consider that the pH system is represented by a discrete-time nonlinear equation:

$$\begin{aligned} y(k) &= f(y(k-1), \dots, y(k-n_y), \\ u(k-1), \dots, u(k-n_u), d(k), \xi(k)) \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

where k stands for the sampling time, the function $f(\cdot)$ represents m_y -dimensional nonlinear vector mapping of the real plant, while $u(k) \in \mathbb{R}^{m_u}$, $y(k) \in \mathbb{R}^{m_y}$, $d(k) \in \mathbb{R}^{m_d}$ and $\xi(k) \in \mathbb{R}^{m_\xi}$ are the vectors of plant's manipulated inputs, outputs, unmeasured input disturbances and uncertain system parameters, respectively; whereas n_y and n_u refer to the maximum lags in the process output and input, respectively. Thus, the control objective is to develop a data-driven model such as LSTM that can accurately predict system behavior based on historical input-output data. The LSTM model serves as the prediction model in a Nonlinear Model Predictive Control (NMPC) algorithm. Solving the LSTM model based NMPC leads to an optimal control law which ensures that

maximum lags of the output and input in the model, respectively. It is to be noted that \hat{n}_y and \hat{n}_u may not necessarily be equal to n_y and n_u . Even though different types of neural network can be trained to represent the model structure, $f_m(\cdot)$. This study adopts an LSTM neural network because of its ability in modeling time series data and tackling the problems of long-term dependencies, gradient vanishing and explosion associated with traditional RNN. Using historical input-output data of the plant, a one-step ahead LSTM neural network can be trained to represent the plant model (Eq.2). Let the network's input at time step k , be denoted by $\psi(k)$, which is a vector of previous input-output data.

$$\begin{aligned} \psi(k) &= [u(k-1), \dots, u(k-\hat{n}_u), y(k-1), \dots, \\ & y(k-\hat{n}_y)] \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

Substituting Eq.(3) into (2), we have the output of the LSTM model as

$$y_m(k) = f_{lstm}(\psi(k)) \quad (4)$$

where $f_{lstm}(\cdot)$ is a nonlinear function representing the LSTM neural network model. The number of input signals

to the network, $n_i = \hat{n}_u + \hat{n}_y$. Following the LSTM neural network model architecture given in Figure 1, the output of each gate of the LSTM network at any discrete time, k is given by:

$$f(k) = \sigma(W_f\psi(k-1) + R_f h(k-1) + b_f) \quad (5)$$

$$i(k) = \sigma(W_i\psi(k-1) + R_i h(k-1) + b_i) \quad (6)$$

$$g(k) = \tanh(W_g\psi(k-1) + R_g h(k-1) + b_g) \quad (7)$$

$$o(k) = \sigma(W_o\psi(k-1) + R_o h(k-1) + b_o) \quad (8)$$

The cell state at time k is given by

$$c(k) = f(k) \otimes c(k-1) + i(k) \otimes g(k) \quad (9)$$

where the symbol \otimes denotes the Hadamard product (i.e., element by element multiplication of vectors)

The hidden state at time k is given by

$$h(k) = o(k) \otimes \sigma(c(k)) \quad (10)$$

The final output given $y_m(k)$ of the LSTM model is given by

$$y_m(k) = W_y h(k) + b_y \quad (11)$$

In Eqs. (5)-(10), the variables i, f, g , and o denote the input gate, forget gate, cell candidate, and output gate, respectively which have a similar dimension of $n_N \times 1$, where N is the number of cells in the network. The learnable parameters of the LSTM layer are usually the input weight, W , the recurrent weight, R and the bias, b . The matrices W, R and b are usually concatenations of the inputs weights, the recurrent weights and bias of each gate that makes up the LSTM layer. The concatenated matrices are given as

$$W = \begin{bmatrix} W_i \\ W_f \\ W_g \\ W_o \end{bmatrix}, R = \begin{bmatrix} R_i \\ R_f \\ R_g \\ R_o \end{bmatrix}, b = \begin{bmatrix} b_i \\ b_f \\ b_g \\ b_o \end{bmatrix}$$

In Eq. (11), W_y and b_y represent output weight and bias respectively. The network uses both sigmoid and tanh activation functions given by Eqs. 12 & 13 respectively.

$$\sigma(x) = \frac{1}{1+e^{-x}} \quad (12)$$

$$\tanh(x) = \frac{e^x - e^{-x}}{e^x + e^{-x}} \quad (13)$$

The determination of the parameters of the LSTM neural network model (i.e, the weights, W, W_y and R ; and the biases, b and b_y) involves minimizing the cost function (RMSE) given in Eq.14.

$$RMSE = \sqrt{\frac{1}{n} \sum_{k=1}^n (y_m(k) - y(k))^2} \quad (14)$$

where $y(k)$ and $y_m(k)$ represent the actual observed value and predicted of output at time, k respectively.

Nonlinear Model Predictive Control Based on LSTM Model

By recursively using Eqs. (5)-(11), the multi-step-ahead predictions can be obtained throughout the prediction horizon. Thus, the LSTM-model based NMPC control problem is then formulated as finding the control inputs over the control horizon, i.e., $u(k+i), \dots, u(k+N_c-1)$, which minimize the cost function:

$$J = \min \left\{ \sum_{i=1}^{N_p} \|r(k+i) - y_p(k+i)\|_{w_y}^2 + \sum_{i=0}^{N_c-1} \|\Delta u(k+i)\|_{w_{\Delta u}}^2 \right\} \quad (15)$$

subject to:

$$y_p(k+i) = f_{lstm}(\psi(k+i)) + d_o(k+i) \quad i = 1, \dots, N_p \quad (16)$$

$$\Delta u_{min} \leq \Delta u(k+i) \leq \Delta u_{max} \quad i = 0, \dots, N_c - 1 \quad (17)$$

$$u_{min} \leq u(k+i) \leq u_{max} \quad i = 0, \dots, N_c - 1 \quad (18)$$

$$y_{min} \leq y_p(k+i) \leq y_{max} \quad i = 1, \dots, N_p \quad (19)$$

$$u(i) = u(k+N_c-1) \text{ for all } i > k+N_c-1 \quad (20)$$

$$\Delta u(k+i) = u(k+i) - u(k+i-1) \quad i = 0, \dots, N_c - 1 \quad (21)$$

where N_p and N_c are the prediction and control horizons respectively; w_y and $w_{\Delta u}$ are the output and input rate weighing matrices respectively; r is the setpoint trajectory. In this formulation, Eq.16 stands for the LSTM neural network model. Eqs. (17) to (19) stand for constraints on process input rates, inputs and outputs respectively. Eq. (20) indicates that the manipulated input is assumed to be constant after the control horizon. The variable $d_o(k)$ in Eq.16 is referred to as the output disturbance. It is being used to correct for any plant-model mismatch that may arise. It is calculated as:

$$d_o(k) = y(k) - y_m(k) \quad (22)$$

The estimated output error is assumed to be constant throughout the prediction horizon. That is,

$$d_o(k+i) = d_o(k); \quad i = 1, \dots, N_p \quad (23)$$

METHODOLOGY

The pH Process Description and Modelling

The pH neutralization process considered here consists of an acid (HNO_3) stream with flowrate u_3 and reaction invariant W_{a3} and W_{b3} , a base (NaOH), with flowrate u_1 and reaction invariant W_{a1} and W_{b1} and a buffer

(NaHCO₃) stream with flowrate u_2 and reaction invariant W_{a2} and W_{b2} that are mixed in a constant-volume (V) stirred tank as described in Henson and Seborg (1994) and Zarzycki and Ławryńczuk (2022). Model assumptions include: perfect mixing, constant density and complete solubility of ions involved. The conserved quantities are the reaction invariants and not the pH. The two reaction invariants on which the formulation will be based are W_{ai} (which is a charge related quantity) and W_{bi} (which is a concentration related quantity); where i represents the three inlet streams 1, 2 and 3. Figure 1 depicts this process.

Figure 2: LSTM-NMPC Control of pH Process

If the reaction invariants for the effluent solutions are represented as W_a and W_b , the following differential equations can then be written for their conservation within the process:

$$V \frac{dW_a}{dt} = u_3(W_{a3} - W_a) + u_1(W_{a1} - W_a) + u_2(W_{a2} - W_a) \quad (24)$$

$$V \frac{dW_b}{dt} = u_3(W_{b3} - W_b) + u_1(W_{b1} - W_b) + u_2(W_{b2} - W_b) \quad (25)$$

The pH of the process can then be determined from W_a and W_b using the following relation:

$$W_a + 10^{pH-14} - 10^{-pH} + W_b \frac{1+2 \times 10^{pH-pk_2}}{1+10^{pk_1-pH}+10^{pH-pk_2}} = 0 \quad (26)$$

where pk_1 and pk_2 are the first and second disassociation constants of the weak acid H₂CO₃. The nominal operating conditions of the system are given in Table 1. The objective here is to control the pH of the effluent solution by manipulating the base flow rate despite the variations of the unmeasured buffer flow rate, which can be considered as unmeasured disturbance.

Design of the Proposed LSTM-NMPC

The method for the design of the proposed LSTM-NMPC is here given in Algorithm 1.

Algorithm 1: The procedure for the design of the proposed LSTM-NMPC

(A) Experiment design for data collection

- i) Identify variables that can influence the process dynamics.
- ii) Design a multi-level random signal for the identified variable(s) in (i).
- iii) Excite the process with the designed signal(s) in (ii) and collect input-output data.
- iv) Split the dataset into training and testing sets

(B) Data preprocessing

- i) Normalize the input-output data to ensure they are within the same range. Normalization within (0 and 1) or (-1 and 1) is often recommended.
- ii) Filter the data to remove noise and outliers
- iii) Convert the input-output data into a time series structure

(C) Model structure and order selection

- i) Chose the appropriate machine learning model
- ii) Select the order of the model (i.e., \hat{n}_x and \hat{n}_y in Eq.2)

(D) Model training

- i) Select the model structure, i.e., the input/fully-connected/LSTM/regression layers
- ii) Select the hyperparameters, i.e., the learning rate, number of neurons, number of layers and tune them
- iii) Use the training dataset to fit the selected model

(E) Model testing

- i) Use the testing dataset to determine the performance of the model
- ii) Use metrics such as mean squared error (MSE), root mean squared error (RMSE) to determine model accuracy.

(F) Model deployment for LSTM-NMPC design

- i) Select NMPC tuning parameters
- ii) Use the trained LSTM as internal prediction model in NMPC and solve nonlinear programming problem in Eqs. (15) to (21).

(G) Closed-loop simulations

- i) Implement the designed LSTM-NMPC on the SIMULINK model of the process
- ii) Conduct both servo and regulatory simulation

(H) Deployment of designed LSTM-NMPC to process test-rig.

If the test rig is available, deploy the designed LSTM-NMPC in real-time using controller board such as dSPACE, Arduino or SCADA system.

Input-Output Data Collection

Following the steps in algorithm 1 and with the governing laws of the pH process as a prior-knowledge, base flow rate is one of the most sensitive variables to pH control and is easily manipulated. So, it is selected as the excitation signal. A multi-level base flow rate signal was then designed to excite the SIMULINK model of the pH process. A very rich input-output dataset was collected for training the LSTM neural network model. The input signal was constrained between 0 and 35ml/sec while the switching times between levels were taken as 300, 150, 75, 20 and 5 seconds respectively. By sampling at the rate of 10 seconds, 7200 input-output dataset was collected and plotted in Figure 3.

Figure 3. Input-Output Data for LSTM Training

LSTM Neural Network Model Development

The variables \hat{n}_u and \hat{n}_y in the LSTM network allows the order of the lagged input and output to be varied by the designer. The order of the trained LSTM model was selected as $\hat{n}_y = 0$ and $\hat{n}_u = 1$. This is because a pH process has a fast dynamics and can be well approximated with a first order model. Lagged outputs are not used as inputs to the model because the model already has a recurrent hidden layer with variables, $h(k)$ and $c(k)$, which provides the model with feedback. Thus, the LSTM model is given as:

$$y(k) = f_{lstm}(u(k - 1)) \quad (27)$$

Table 1: pH Process Nominal Operating Conditions

$u_3 = 16.60$ ml/s	$u_2 = 0.55$ ml/s
$u_1 = 15.55$ ml/s	$V = 2900$ ml
$W_{a1} = -3.05 \times 10^{-3}$ mol	$W_{a2} = -3 \times 10^{-2}$ mol
$W_{a3} = 3 \times 10^{-3}$ mol	$W_a = -4.32 \times 10^{-4}$ mol
$W_{b1} = 5 \times 10^{-5}$ mol	$W_{b2} = 3 \times 10^{-2}$ mol
$W_{b3} = 0$ mol	$W_b = 5.28 \times 10^{-4}$ mol
$pk_1 = 6.35$	$pk_2 = -10.25$
$y = 7.0$	

The LSTM neural network architecture was designed with 1 sequence input later; 2 LSTM layers with 10 neurons each; 1 fully connected layer with 1 neuron. MATLAB

Deep learning toolbox was used in training the LSTM model with a performance index of RMSE, training algorithm of Adam, initial learning rate of 0.01 and Maximum epoch of 5000.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Validation Results of the Identified LSTM Model

The performance of the trained LSTM model was compared with the first principle (FP) model (i.e., the ODE) of the pH and the linear model of the pH obtained at the nominal operating condition described in Table 1. The linearized model is given by:

$$\begin{bmatrix} \frac{dx_1}{dt} \\ \frac{dx_2}{dt} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} -0.01128 & 0 \\ 0 & -0.01128 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \\ x_2 \end{bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} -9.028 \times 10^{-7} \\ -1.648 \times 10^{-7} \end{bmatrix} u_1 \quad (28)$$

$$y = [-5481 \quad -4485] \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \\ x_2 \end{bmatrix} \quad (29)$$

Figure 4 gives a comparison between the openloop response of the nonlinear ODE model of pH process, the trained LSTM model and the linearized model when perturbed with stair step changes in the manipulated input. The result reveals that the LSTM neural network model gave a very good fit with a mean square error (MSE) of 0.0094 and prediction which closely matched that of the original pH process thus, showing that the trained LSTM model was able to capture the pH inherent nonlinearity. The linearized model however showed a poor fit with a MSE of 0.28. The steady state input-output characteristics of the pH neutralization process was plotted in Figure 5. This plot showed that the trained LSTM model has the same steady-state characteristics (i.e., S-shape) with the pH process. The steady-state characteristics of the linear model was however just a straight line which shows a direct proportion between the pH response and the base flow rate.

Simulation Results

The trained LSTM model was then used in designing a LSTM-based NMPC with the tuning parameters selected as $N_p = 15$, $N_c = 1$, $w_y = 1$, $w_{\Delta u} = 0.75$. For the purpose of comparison, first principle model based NMPC (i.e., FP-NMPC) and linear MPC (i.e., LMPC) were equally designed with the tuning parameters chosen to be the same for fair comparison. Both set-point tracking and disturbance rejection scenarios were investigated.

The closed-loop servo response plotted in Figure 6 showed that the proposed LSTM-NMPC displayed perfect setpoint tracking which closed match the performance of FP-NMPC with IAE values of 674 and 656 respectively. The response of LMPC was however worse with an IAE value of 1052. In order to test the disturbance rejection ability of the designed LSTM-NMPC, the buffer flow rate, u_2 was changed from its nominal value of 0.55ml/s as

shown in Eq.30. The closed-loop regulatory response plotted in Figure 7 showed that the proposed LSTM-NMPC gave a perfect disturbance rejection which closely matched the reponse of FP-NMPC with respective IAE values of 180 and 172. LMPC gave a slightly worse performance with an IAE value of 325.

Figure 4: Openloop Response of the pH Process, the LSTM and Linear Model to Stair Step Changes in the Base Flow Rate.

Figure 5: Steady-state Input-Output Characteristics of the pH Process, the Trained LSTM and Linear Models.

$$u_2(t) = \begin{cases} 0.55, & 0 \leq t \leq 1800 \\ 1.20, & 1800 < t \leq 3600 \\ 2.00, & 3600 < t \leq 5400 \\ 1.00, & 5400 < t \leq 7200 \\ 0.20, & 7200 < t \leq 9000 \\ 0.55, & 9000 < t \leq 12000 \end{cases} \quad (30)$$

Figure 6: Closed-loop Servo Results of the pH Process

Figure 7: Closed-loop Regulatory Results of the pH Process

CONCLUSION

In this study, a long short-term memory (LSTM) network-based nonlinear model predictive control was developed and applied to a pH neutralization process. The developed LSTM model demonstrated exceptional ability in capturing the complex dynamics and high nonlinearity of the neutralization process, significantly outperforming linear models in terms of prediction accuracy. The closed-loop servo and regulatory results revealed that the proposed LSTM-based NMPC maintained excellent pH control even in the presence of unmeasured disturbances and variable operating conditions. This highlights the potential of LSTM networks for control applications in complex chemical processes. Further studies could explore the use of physics-informed LSTM networks and Neural Ordinary Differential Equations (Neural ODEs).

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